

1 **Supplementary material.**

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Figure S1. Spatial distribution of the ichthyoplankton samples for the two periods: 2001-2005 and 2012-2015.

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10 **Figure S2.** Larvae abundances (number of larvae per square meter) of Bongo 90 towed down to the mixed
 11 layer depth and Bongo 60 towed down to 70 meters. Data from experimental fishing to calibrate gear
 12 catchability on bluefin tuna larvae ($R^2=0.998$; $CPUA-B90ml = (a*CPUA B60do)*(exp(b*CPUA B60do))$; $a=$
 13 0.5823 ; $b=0.00115$; model and figure from Alvarez-Berastegui et al, 2017)

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22 **Figure S3.** A,B: Filtered volumes by bongo nets (A: bongo 90, B: bongo 60); C: Temporal distribution of
23 samples over day of the year; D: Larval length distributions; E: mean temperature in the mixed layer depth;
24 F: mean salinity in the mixed layer depth. Red dotted lines indicating the mean value of each variable for the
25 entire data set.

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29 **Figure S4.** Mean sea surface temperature in the ichthyoplankton survey area from ROMS hydrodynamic
 30 models during June and July. Red line showing mean value for the entire data set.

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33 **Figure S5.** A: Number of albacore larvae and B: CPUA along dates for all campaigns. Note the zero catches
 34 along most of the 2002 campaign (samples in red) distributed from day 158 (8 June) to 179 (29 June).

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37 **Figure S6. A:** Receiver Operating Characteristic curve (ROC) of the binomial model and correspondent Area
 38 Under the Curve (AUC); **B.** Predicted presence probability distributions (density plot) for the real presences
 39 (blue) and real absences (pink).

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42 **Figure S7.** Lognormal model diagnostic plots.

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